

Infrared Spectra of N-Hydroxy-N,N'-Diarylbenedamides

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Condensation of N-arylbenedamoyl chlorides with N-phenylhydroxylamine in absolute ether medium furnished N-hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-arylbenedamides. Seven such new compounds have been synthesized and their infrared spectra examined. The probable assignments have been made for the principal bands, $C=N^+=NH$, $C=N$, $C-N$ and $OH \cdots N$. The studies provided evidence that the intramolecular $OH \cdots N$ bonds are stronger than $OH \cdots O$ bonds.

N-HYDROXY-N, N'-disubstituted benzedamides are synthesized for their possible use as analytical reagents^{1,2}. The new compounds are prepared by the condensation of N-arylbenedamoyl chlorides, I and N-phenylhydroxylamine, II in absolute ether medium. The reagents, III, can be regarded as derivatives of

of amidines. N-derivatives of amidines are named by designating the nitrogen of the $-NH_2$ group N and the nitrogen of $=NH$ group N'. It may be seen that hydroxylamine, IV itself gives the amidoxime, V which is tautomeric with the N-hydroxybenzedamide form, VI.

N-Arylhydroxylamines give the expected products as they cannot tautomerize to the respective amidoximes.

Synthesis of benzedamoyl chlorides : In the present investigation the imidoyl chlorides have been synthesized following essentially the procedure of Wallach and coworkers⁴; phosphorus pentachloride being replaced by thionyl chloride. The anilides listed in Table I are employed for the preparation of N-arylbenedamoyl chlorides.

TABLE 1—ANILIDES AND CORRESPONDING IMIDOYL CHLORIDES

Benzoyl	- benzedamoyl chloride
- aniline	N-Phenyl
- p-toluidine	N-p-Tolyl
- m-toluidine	N-m-Tolyl
- o-chloroaniline	N-o-Chlorophenyl
- p-chloroaniline	N-p-Chlorophenyl
- p-anisidine	N-p-Anisyl

Synthesis of compounds : These are prepared by the reaction of N-arylbenedamoyl chloride with N-phenylhydroxylamine in absolute ether^{1,2}. In Table 2 are reported four hydroxyamidine free bases and three hydrochlorides synthesized using the same experimental conditions and molecular proportions of the reactants. The hydrochlorides form white shining crystals, soluble in alcohol, acetone; sparingly soluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene and ether. In hot water, they are slowly hydrolyzed to the corresponding free bases. The hydroxyamidine free bases are stable pale yellow to yellow solids, soluble in common organic solvents and insoluble in water.

Infrared spectra : The important group frequencies of four free bases and three hydrochlorides are summarized in Table 3. The spectra were recorded as nujol mulls on a Perkin Elmer model 237 except N-hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-p-tolylbenzedamide hydrochloride which was recorded on Perkin Elmer infracord spectrophotometer. The principal bands associated with the $=\overset{+}{N}H$, $C=N^+$, $C=N$, $C-N$ and $O-H \cdots N$ groups have been assigned. The functional grouping, VII in hydroxy-

TABLE 2—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES OF N-HYDROXY-N,N'-DISUBSTITUTED BENZAMIDINES

Compound No	benzamidine	m p. °C	yield %	Formula	Found %			Calcd %		
					C	H	N	C	H	N
1	N-Hydroxy-N,N'-diphenyl	163	28	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	79.06	5.62	9.87	79.16	5.55	9.72
2	N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-p-tolyl-	190	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	79.56	5.85	9.13	79.47	5.96	9.27
3	N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-p-anisyl-	170	32	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	75.67	5.75	8.79	75.47	5.66	8.80
4	N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-p-chlorophenyl-	185	39	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ OCl	70.86	4.85	8.65	70.69	4.65	8.68
5	N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-p-tolylbenzamidinium hydrochloride	201	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ OCl	70.82	5.54	8.12	70.90	5.61	8.27
6	N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-m-tolylbenzamidinium hydrochloride	191	67	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ OCl	71.08	5.56	8.02	70.90	5.61	8.27
7	N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-o-chlorophenylbenzamidinium hydrochloride	196	5	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ OCl	63.89	4.74	7.77	63.51	4.45	7.80

TABLE 3—INFRARED STRETCHING FREQUENCIES IN HYDROXYAMIDINES (CM⁻¹)

Compd. No (Table 2)	OH	Ar-H	Ammonium band + =NH	Immonium band + C=NH	C=N	C-N	N-O
1	3080	3040 Sh			1601	1425 Sh.S	940
2	3080	3050 Sh			1600	1410 Sh.S	940
3	3080	3040 Sh			1602	1415 Sh.S	940
4	30:0	3040 Sh			1600	1410 Sh.S	940
5	—	3050 Sh	2575 BS	1630 Sh.S	—	—	940
6	—	3040 Sh	25:0 BS	1625 Sh.S	—	—	935
7	—	3040 Sh	2575 BS	1630 Sh.S	—	—	930

The spectra were recorded as nujol mulls. (not shown)

Sh-Sharp ; BS-Broad Strong ; Sh.S-Sharp Strong.

amidines permits the formation of a strong intramolecular O-H...N bond. The OH stretching absorption in these compounds appears at 3080 cm⁻¹. This large shift from free OH absorption is indicative of strong intramolecular H-bonding. The studies revealed that the intramolecular hydrogen bonding has no influence on the C=N stretching absorption. Hydroxyl group frequency shift also provided evidence that intramolecular OH...N bonds are stronger than OH...O bonds. In N-arylhydroxamic acids⁵ containing the grouping, VIII, the OH absorption occurs at 3200 cm⁻¹ and in N-hydroxy-N, N'-diarylbenzamidines, IX, this band is observed at 3080 cm⁻¹.

C=N Stretching vibration : In the hydroxyamidines examined, the C=N bond stretching bands have been assigned in the 1600 cm⁻¹ region. Phenyl groups also absorb in the same region presenting difficulties in the unambiguous assignment of the C=N stretching absorption. In the present study the C=N band assignment is made on the basis of the C=N absorption in benzylideneaniline, X and amidines, XI.

C=N stretching absorption generally appears between 1640-1690 cm⁻¹. In benzylideneaniline, X, the C=N stretching vibration appears at 1627 cm⁻¹. This lowering of C=N absorption in benzylideneaniline is attributed to conjugation. The N-mono, XI, and N, N'-disubstituted amidines⁶ show their characteristic C=N absorption at 1582-1600 cm⁻¹.

The lowering of C=N bond frequency to 1600 cm⁻¹ from 1627 cm⁻¹ in benzylideneaniline and the shift of C-N from 1044 cm⁻¹ in methylamine⁷ to 1410-1425 cm⁻¹ in hydroxyamidines may be attributed to the mesomeric structures, XII and XIII. Using Luttké's

correlation⁸ for the C-N bond length and C-N stretching frequencies, the observed frequency at 1410 cm⁻¹ would correspond approximately to a C-N bond length of 1.36 Å. Some contribution from the dipolar structure is indicated by the results of n.m.r studies of amidines which show that the 'single' C-N bond is significantly short and that rotation about it is restricted⁹.

The C-N stretching band observed at 1410-1425 cm⁻¹ in the hydroxyamidine free bases disappeared

